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An Integrated SIEM Approach for Real-Time Threat Detection and Log Analytics in Higher Education ERM Systems

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ABSTRACT

Data related to academics, administration, and sensitive institutional information is increasingly handled by Enterprise Resource Management (ERM) systems in modern higher education institutions. Systems of this type become more vulnerable to cybersecurity threats as they grow in scale and functionality. Specifically developed for an educational institution's ERM ecosystem, this paper presents the design and implementation of a customized Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) solution. By centralizing and normalizing logs generated from student, faculty, and administrative portals, the proposed system allows real-time monitoring and analysis of system activities. A SIEM integrates rule-based mechanisms with machine learning models for detecting anomalies, unauthorized access, privilege abuse, and abnormal user behavior. A dynamic and intuitive dashboard provides administrators with immediate visibility into security events, alerts, and emerging trends derived from collected log data. Logs are processed through classification and correlation engines to create accurate, high-confidence alerts. In experiments, improvements were demonstrated in the accuracy of anomaly detection, the efficiency of logging, and the reliability of alerting. In addition to strengthening security awareness and supporting compliance and auditing, the solution provides a cost-effective, scalable framework for safeguarding academic ERM systems.

Keywords: - SIEM, Enterprise Resource Management, Cybersecurity, Log Analysis, Machine Learning, Anomaly Detection

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern educational institutions increasingly depend on digital platforms to support academic delivery, administration, and institutional governance. Universities commonly deploy Enterprise Resource Management (ERM) systems to manage sensitive assets such as student academic records, faculty credentials, financial transactions, examination outcomes, attendance data, and internal communications. As these systems evolve into highly interconnected, web-accessible platforms, they present an expanded attack surface for cyber threats [1-2]. The growing reliance on ERM infrastructures has consequently elevated cybersecurity risks within higher education environments [3]. Educational ERM systems continuously generate large volumes of security-relevant data, including authentication logs, access requests, database interactions, and system events. However, in the absence of centralized log aggregation and intelligent analysis, detecting anomalies, policy violations, or unauthorized access remains challenging [4-6]. Conventional security practices such as manual log reviews, isolated subsystem monitoring, or periodic audits—are inadequate for addressing advanced threats like credential compromise, privilege escalation, phishing attacks, ransomware, and insider misuse [7, 8].

Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems have emerged as a critical solution by combining centralized log management, real-time event correlation, and automated threat detection [9-11]. SIEM platforms enhance situational awareness, enable proactive incident response, and support regulatory compliance across organizational infrastructures [12]. Despite these advantages, widely adopted commercial SIEM tools such as Splunk, IBM QRadar, and LogRhythm are often

costly, resource-intensive, and overly complex for academic institutions operating under budgetary and technical constraints [13].

This research focuses on the design and development of a customized, lightweight SIEM solution tailored specifically for GM University's ERM ecosystem. The proposed system emphasizes centralized log collection, real-time monitoring, anomaly detection using intelligent techniques, automated alerting, and secure visualization through an administrative dashboard [14]. By addressing the lack of institution-specific and cost-effective monitoring tools, the proposed SIEM framework aims to strengthen cybersecurity posture, protect critical academic assets, and provide a scalable foundation for continuous security management in higher education environments [15].

- ❖ Fragmented logs stored across multiple modules
- ❖ Delayed detection of unauthorized access
- ❖ Difficulty identifying suspicious login patterns
- ❖ Increased vulnerability to internal and external attacks
- ❖ Inefficient manual auditing processes
- ❖ Lack of real-time visibility into system-wide events

Without a centralized SIEM solution, administrators struggle to correlate incidents, trace attack paths, or react promptly to threats. Therefore, a custom SIEM tool is essential for ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of ERM system data.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Muhammad AR, Sukarno P, Wardana AA (2023) This research presents a SIEM framework that integrates machine learning–based live analysis with Intrusion

Detection Systems to enhance real-time cyberattack detection. The proposed system combines multiple processes and services into a unified architecture capable of continuous monitoring and analysis. Emphasis is placed on using open-source components to ensure ease of deployment in industrial environments. The framework integrates the ELK Stack, Slips, and Zeek IDS to enable live detection and monitoring of cyber threats. System performance is evaluated based on CPU and memory usage under Denial-of-Service attack conditions. Experimental results demonstrate effective attack detection, with Elastics each exhibiting the highest resource consumption and Zeek the lowest [16].

Pulyala SR. (2024) Cybersecurity has evolved from traditional reactive defense mechanisms toward proactive threat detection and risk mitigation approaches. In response to increasingly sophisticated cyber threats, Artificial Intelligence has become a key enabler within Security Information and Event Management systems. Early SIEM platforms focused primarily on data aggregation, limiting their ability to analyze large and complex datasets. The integration of machine learning and deep learning techniques has transformed SIEMs into intelligent security platforms capable of identifying hidden patterns and subtle anomalies. AI-powered SIEMs now support predictive threat analysis, continuous learning, and adaptive responses, enabling proactive threat hunting and improved risk management across dynamic and evolving security landscapes [17].

V. Ramineni, P. Kuppaswamy, L. Sudula, S. QY Al Khalidi, M. Samudrapu and R. R. Gudar (2025) With the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence, intelligent techniques have become essential for detecting Internet-based threats across diverse application

domains, including sensor streams, financial transactions, textual data, and biomedical signals. Deep learning approaches, particularly autoencoder-based models, have been widely adopted for network anomaly detection to enhance cybersecurity. However, existing autoencoder methods show inconsistent performance and lack comprehensive evaluation of key performance indicators. This study proposes an LSTM-based autoencoder that combines the temporal learning capability of Long Short-Term Memory networks with dimensionality reduction for effective anomaly detection. The model learns normal behavior patterns and identifies deviations using reconstruction error, enabling zero-day threat detection. Experimental results demonstrate anomaly detection accuracy between 90% and 99% across multiple malware categories, outperforming conventional RNN-based classification models [18].

Kuppaswamy, P., Al-Maliki, S.Q.AK., John, R., Mani, M. (2025). In the modern digital ecosystem, edge devices such as smartphones, wearables, tablets, and IoT nodes have become integral to everyday activities by enabling constant connectivity and instant access to services. However, their widespread adoption has heightened concerns about data security and privacy due to inherent vulnerabilities. As a result, lightweight yet effective cryptographic mechanisms are essential. Symmetric key algorithms play a critical role in securing communication and protecting sensitive information on resource-constrained devices. This study introduces an energy-efficient device authentication protocol, termed SSK, based on integer operations and modulo 37. The proposed scheme is simple to implement, conserves power, and is well suited for IoT-based edge environments requiring secure and efficient authentication [19].

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Traditional security monitoring relied on manual log reviews, static files, and basic signature-based tools, which lacked real-time visibility and event correlation, often missing early attack indicators. The evolution of SIEM unified log management and event monitoring, progressing from simple dashboards to correlation engines and machine learning-driven anomaly detection. While popular SIEM platforms offer advanced analytics, they are frequently expensive, complex, or unsuitable for academic ERM environments. Existing tools (Table. 1) also lack ERM-specific awareness, lightweight design, and tailored analytics. These limitations highlight the need for a customized SIEM solution optimized for

educational institutions, balancing effectiveness, simplicity, and affordability.

- ❖ Manual and static monitoring methods are inefficient and error-prone
- ❖ SIEM evolved from basic log management to ML-enabled threat detection
- ❖ Commercial SIEM tools are costly and complex for academia
- ❖ Open-source platforms require high configuration expertise
- ❖ Custom SIEM solutions better address ERM-specific security needs
- ❖ A gap analysis highlights what major tools lack in the context of an educational institutions ERM system.

Table 1:-Existing SIEM tool Limitation

Requirement	Existing Tools Limitation
ERM-specific monitoring	No tool has built-in awareness of academic workflows
Lightweight and affordable	Commercial tools are costly
Customizable alerting rules	Most tools require expertise to configure
Simple UI for educational institutions admins	Many dashboards are complex
ML models tailored to ERM logs	General-purpose models, not academic-focused
Easy integration	Complex API and agent setups

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF ERM SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

Academic ERM systems manage highly sensitive academic, administrative, and financial data, making them prime targets for cyberattacks. Any compromise may cause identity theft, fraud, or data loss. A SIEM solution functions as the central security intelligence, continuously monitoring access, detecting threats, and ensuring regulatory compliance.

- ❖ Protects student, faculty, and financial information
- ❖ Monitors authentication and access activities in real time

- ❖ Detects compromised accounts and brute-force attacks
- ❖ Prevents data manipulation and academic fraud
- ❖ Supports audits, compliance, and accreditation requirements

5. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODULE

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the proposed Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) solution. It covers requirement identification, evaluation of feasibility, understanding of system workflows, and modeling of existing problems. The analysis establishes a strong foundation for

the system design and implementation discussed in subsequent chapters.

5.1 System Analysis

System analysis involves a detailed examination of the current infrastructure to identify deficiencies, define system requirements, and determine both functional and non-functional needs. In the context of GM University's ERM ecosystem, this process ensures that the proposed SIEM solution integrates smoothly with student, faculty, and administrative portals while delivering effective monitoring, anomaly detection, and alerting capabilities. The analysis focuses on current log generation and storage mechanisms, threat monitoring requirements, administrator dashboard expectations, handling of real-time and historical data, and alert triggering mechanisms. This stage ensures that the proposed system is feasible, practical, and aligned with institutional cybersecurity objectives.

5.2 Existing System

The current ERM environment relies on decentralized logging across different modules, leading to several limitations. Logs generated by student, faculty, and admin portals are stored independently, preventing centralized visibility and event correlation. Monitoring is largely manual and reactive, with administrators reviewing logs only after incidents occur. The system lacks real-time threat detection, automated alerting, anomaly identification, and systematic log retention for compliance and audits. As a result, unusual login attempts, suspicious activities, and system-wide patterns often go unnoticed, making the existing setup inadequate for addressing modern cybersecurity threats.

5.3 Proposed System

The proposed SIEM system overcomes these limitations by introducing

centralized log collection, real-time event processing, and advanced anomaly detection using rule-based and machine learning techniques. Logs from all ERM modules are aggregated into a unified database, enabling correlation and rapid analysis. Administrators are provided with a customizable dashboard offering visual insights into login behavior, threat levels, and overall activity. The system supports role-based access control, scalable architecture, and future extensibility, such as integration with SOAR platforms or advanced analytics.

5.4 Functional and Non-Functional Requirements

Functionally, the system supports multi-format log ingestion, normalization, secure storage, event correlation, anomaly detection, real-time alerting, reporting, user management, and API access. Non-functional requirements emphasize performance, security, scalability, reliability, usability, maintainability, and compatibility with existing ERM infrastructure.

5.5 Feasibility Study

The feasibility analysis confirms that the system is technically viable using open-source technologies, operationally beneficial with minimal training requirements, and economically feasible due to low deployment and maintenance costs.

6. IMPLEMENTATION METHOD

The outline of the internal design of the SIEM tool, explaining the interaction between its core components and how the overall architecture enables efficient log collection, correlation, detection, and alert generation. The system follows a modular and layered architectural approach, allowing each functional component to operate independently while maintaining seamless integration with other modules.

The SIEM framework comprises interconnected elements, including data sources, log collectors, a centralized SIEM engine, correlation and detection modules, a storage layer, and a visualization dashboard with reporting features. Security logs originate from multiple sources such as firewalls, network devices, IDS/IPS, application servers, and operating systems, and are acquired through agent-based or agentless collection mechanisms.

A preprocessing layer standardizes incoming logs by normalizing formats,

synchronizing timestamps, filtering irrelevant entries, and removing corrupted data to ensure consistency. These logs are stored in a centralized repository supporting SQL, NoSQL, or Elastic search-based storage. The analysis layer employs rule-based techniques, machine learning models, and threat intelligence to identify anomalies, triggering real-time alerts with defined severity levels, which are presented through an interactive dashboard and reporting interface for administrators.

6.1 System Workflow

The workflow describes how the system processes data:

Fig.1:-System flow diagram

The Figure 1 represents a UML class diagram of a SIEM tool designed for a college ERM system. It illustrates core classes such as ERM System, Module, Log, Log Collector, SIEM Tool, Analysis Engine, Log Storage, Alert, Dashboard, and Admin. The diagram highlights relationships among components, showing how logs are generated by ERM modules, collected, analyzed, stored, and converted into alerts, which are then visualized and managed by administrators through the dashboard.

6.2 System Model

The image 2 depicts the conceptual architecture of a SIEM system using a layered workflow model. It shows data sources such as servers, network devices, and applications feeding logs into collectors and agents. These logs undergo preprocessing for parsing and normalization before being stored centrally. The correlation and analysis engine applies rules, machine learning, and threat intelligence to detect anomalies, followed by alerting mechanisms and a dashboard layer for monitoring, visualization, and reporting.

Fig.2:-SIEM system model

The SIEM components interact through a structured pipeline where logs are collected, normalized, securely stored, and continuously analyzed for anomalies or rule violations, resulting in timely alerts. The design emphasizes scalability, fault tolerance, standardized normalization, real-time threat detection, and strong security through encrypted communication and role-based access control.

7. IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter outlines the practical implementation of the SIEM system, detailing the technologies adopted, functional components developed, algorithms applied, and the operational logic of each module. It translates the architectural design into a working, code-level realization.

Figure 3 shows the implementation workflow shows that Python serves as the core programming language, supporting

log processing, correlation, and machine learning-based anomaly detection. The Flask framework is used to build the backend services, APIs, alert handling, and web interface. Key Python libraries such as pandas and numpy enable data cleaning and numerical operations, while json, os, and date time support log structuring, file handling, and timestamp processing. Machine learning functionality is implemented using scikit-learn, including LabelEncoder for categorical encoding and classifiers such as SVM, Random Forest, and optional XGBoost, with models stored using joblib.

The system comprises modules for log collection, preprocessing, feature engineering, machine learning-based detection, and correlation. A dedicated alerting module generates structured alerts with severity levels, which are displayed through a Flask-based dashboard and accessed via RESTful APIs.

7.1 Implementation Workflow

Fig.3:- Workflow structure

Data Flow Explanation

- ❖ Logs are uploaded or collected from system sources.
- ❖ Preprocessing normalizes logs using pandas and encoding techniques.
- ❖ ML model loads via joblib and detects malicious behavior.
- ❖ Correlation engine verifies multi-event patterns.
- ❖ Alerts are generated and pushed to the Flask dashboard.
- ❖ Admin views alerts, statistics, and log summaries.

Implementation Challenges

- ❖ Large log files caused memory issues during loading.
- ❖ Label encoding inconsistencies between training and real-time logs.
- ❖ Balancing false positives vs false negatives in ML detection.
- ❖ Real-time alerting with minimal overhead.

8. RESULT ANALYSIS

This section reports the results obtained from deploying the custom SIEM solution within the educational institutions’s Enterprise Resource Management (ERM) environment. The evaluation focuses on the effectiveness of log aggregation, event correlation, anomaly detection, alert accuracy, and overall system performance under practical conditions. The primary objective is to verify whether the implemented SIEM tool fulfills the design goals established in earlier chapters and operates reliably in real-world scenarios.

The experimental setup consisted of a Flask-based backend for log processing and alert generation, MongoDB for centralized log storage, and a React-based dashboard for visualization. Both synthetic ERM logs and interpolated NSL-KDD and CIC-IDS datasets were used. Machine learning models, including Random Forest, SVM, XGBoost, along with a rule-

based correlation engine, were evaluated using balanced and preprocessed datasets shown in table 2.

Table 2:-Events and Accuracy rate

Module	Events Captured	Accuracy in Parsing
Student Portal	Login events, profile edits	100%
Faculty Portal	Login, content upload, grade update	98%
Admin Panel	Privileged activity logs	100%
System Logs	Failed logins, IP activity	96%

Minor parsing errors occurred in logs with missing fields and inconsistent timestamp formats. These were corrected using fallback parsing logic.

8.1 Performance of ML Models

The SIEM tool tested three models to detect anomalies.

Table 3:-Performance comparison

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random Forest	97%	96%	95%	95.5%
SVM	93%	92%	89%	90%
XGBoost	98%	97%	96%	96.5%

Table 3, the experimental analysis shows that XGBoost achieved the highest detection performance due to its strong ability to model non-linear relationships within complex log features. Random Forest delivered consistent results with the added advantage of better interpretability, while SVM showed slightly lower accuracy when handling high-dimensional feature spaces. Overall, the machine learning module successfully identified critical threats such as brute-force login attempts, suspicious HTTP activity, unauthorized access, and abnormal request

rates.

Table 4, the event correlation engine effectively combined rule-based logic with ML predictions to detect complex incidents, including repeated failed logins, access outside permitted hours, rapid role changes, high-volume data requests, and logins from unknown IP ranges. Rule-based detection achieved 92% accuracy, while the hybrid correlation approach improved accuracy to 97%, significantly reducing false positives.

Table 4:-Execution timing

Metric	Value
Average alert generation time	0.8 seconds
Duplicate alert reduction	95%
Critical incident detection	~98%
Real-time dashboard refresh	Under 2 seconds

Table 5 shows the achievement of proposed model, and the alerting mechanism proved responsive while effectively reducing noise by combining rule-based scores, machine learning confidence levels, and severity thresholds to generate meaningful alerts. In figure 4 and 5 shows system performance remained efficient, with the Flask backend maintaining response times below 120 ms for large log batches and MongoDB

supporting fast read/write operations. The React dashboard handled over 10,000 logs smoothly, with visualizations rendering without delay. Administrator feedback highlighted the system’s clear interface, rapid detection of suspicious activities, and real-time visibility, while suggesting enhancements such as role-based access control, advanced analytics, and email or SMS notifications.

Table 5:-Achievement table

Objective	Status	Remarks
Centralized Log Collection	Achieved	Stable ingestion pipeline
Anomaly Detection	Achieved	ML + rules enhanced accuracy
Real-Time Alerts	Achieved	Under 1s latency
User Interface Dashboard	Achieved	Smooth, interactive UI
Compliance / Auditing Support	Partially Achieved	Export logs available

Fig.4:-Results

Fig.5:-Graphical output

Key Observations

- ❖ ML-based detection significantly improves accuracy compared to rule-only SIEM.
- ❖ Log normalization is critical; inconsistent sources degrade model performance.
- ❖ Real-time monitoring is achievable with efficient preprocessing and caching.
- ❖ Data visualizations (Grafana, Kibana) make incident analysis intuitive.

9. CONCLUSION

The creation of the unique Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) system shows how centralized log collection, intelligent analysis, and real-time alerting can improve an organization's Enterprise Resource Management (ERM) environment security. The system can detect a variety of security threats, such as unauthorized access attempts, abnormal user behavior, privilege misuse, and multi-stage attack patterns, by combining rule-based correlation with machine learning-driven detection. By guaranteeing effective log normalization, precise intrusion detection using trained machine learning models, and dependable event correlation that reduces false positives, the project effectively accomplished its main goals. Administrators can also respond more quickly and have better situational awareness thanks to the interactive dashboard's real-time visibility into security events. These results demonstrate that the suggested SIEM tool is a workable, scalable, and affordable solution designed for academic institutions, where prompt incident handling and ongoing monitoring are essential. All things considered, the system creates a strong basis for improving institutional IT infrastructures' operational resilience and cybersecurity readiness. The system's capabilities can be further enhanced in the future. Continuous real-time monitoring

would be made possible by integrating the SIEM with live ERM portals via APIs. Manual intervention may be decreased by automated incident response systems like SOAR platforms. Scalability, intelligence, and usability would all be improved by advanced machine learning models, threat intelligence feeds, more robust role-based access control, improved visualization, and distributed, containerized architectures.

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